

SOCIO-POLITICAL VIEWS IN AHMAD DONISH'S "HISTORY OF THE MANGIT DYNASTY"

Akhmedova Zebiniso Azizovna

Head of Department of Social Sciences
Bukhara state medical institute.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11900295>

Abstract. *In this article, the author explores the socio-political views in the historical work of Ahmad Donish "History of the Mangyt Dynasty", the range of problems and current issues. Two works by Ahmad Donish are devoted mainly to problems of history and public administration. This is, first of all, "Nawadir-ul-Waqe", which is the main and most important part of the "Political Treatise", and "it ranks first both in the time of its creation and in its significance."*

Key words: *dynasty, social status, political system, description, analysis, mangyts, historical work.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ В «ИСТОРИИ ДИНАСТИИ МАНГИТА» АХМАДА ДОНИША

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор исследует общественно-политические взгляды в историческом труде Ахмада Дониша «История династии Мангыт», круг проблем и актуальные вопросы. Две работы Ахмада Дониша посвящены преимущественно проблемам истории и государственного управления. Это, прежде всего, «Навадир-уль-Ваке», который является главной и важнейшей частью «Политического трактата» и «он занимает первое место как по времени своего создания, так и по своему значению».*

Ключевые слова: *династия, социальный статус, политическая система, описание, анализ, мангыты, исторический труд.*

Currently, in the Bukhara State Museum-Reserve, Ahmad Donish's draft and original copy of "Mukhtasare az tarikhi sultanati khandano mangitiya" (written in the last years of his life) and "Navodirul waqoe" written by his own hand (i.e. the first book of 1880) is preserved.

The work "Mukhtasare az tarikhi sultanati khandani mangitiya" dedicated to the history of Bukhara emirs (the book is also called "Risela" and "Tarikhcha") begins with the description of the planets, and in the following places Bukhara mangit management and military policy of the emirs, dedicated to memories of a trip to Russia. The original copy of this work kept in the Bukhara Museum has its own history. On September 26, 1959, this book was accepted into the oriental manuscripts fund of the museum by Ahmed Kasimzada, an employee of the Bukhara Museum.

Muhiddinov from Bukhara gave the book to the museum. And the book was a souvenir from his grandfather Qazi Saidahmadi Bukhari. This can be seen from the two seals on the last pages of the book. At one time, Ahmadi was a close friend of Porina. In this regard, the author presented his work to the judge. The book consists of 48 pages and is written in the "shikasta" type of the nastalyq letter. The name of the work and the time of writing are not written anywhere. But in other excerpts, this work is given the above title.

Ahmed Donish's philosophical analysis of state management and political government affairs has kept up with the times and has not lost its relevance to this day. For example, Donish described Amir Daniyol in his pamphlet "A Brief History of Bukhara Mangites": "In the last years

of his reign, he distanced himself from state affairs and gave power to his sons so that they would not observe that he was conducting his administration based on Sharia laws. and distributed to regional governors. Amir Daniel's sons betrayed him. "Also, the never-ending disparate taxes naturally fell on the ordinary, hardworking people," he tries to show the basis of the state's decline.

However, it should also be noted that Ahmad Donish did not live in the time of Amir Daniyal, so he obtained this information from the works of historians and thinkers who lived before him.

In addition, Ahmad Donish gave information about Amir Shahmurad in the introduction of this work and said, "Renovators of religion come to the world every millennium and centenary.

During the renewal period of the religion every hundred years, the first fifty years will be a rapid development and the religion will be strengthened. In the remaining fifty years, there will be a retreat from religion. Therefore, the renovator of this twelfth century is Amir Ma'sum - Amir Shahmurad. At the same time, in the history of Movarounnahr, starting from Amir Temur, he mentions the names of "renovators of religion" every hundred years.

Ahmad Donish, in his pamphlet "Brief History of Bukhara Mangites", critically covered the political processes during the era of Emir Muzaffar and revealed the chaos in the country's administrative management. For example, people named Sherali, Yaqub, Muhammadshah, Durbin, Salimbiy, Barotbek, who studied with the emir, organized their own groups and occupied high positions in the Bukhara Emirate, where they rose to power. regretfully reports that lawlessness and violence have escalated in the country and caused the discontent of the people.

Ahmed Donish admitted that during the reign of Emir Muzaffar, who took the throne of Bukhara from Karmana, oppression in the country increased, farmers were taxed heavily, and no one heard the people's complaints, which is why the decline of the country accelerated.

In the first years of Amir Muzaffar's reign, he gathered an army from the property left by his father and marched to Hisar and Kokhan and occupied several places by force. Disobedient citizens are executed or captured. Proud of this success, the emir tries to subjugate Sharia laws to his will, not recognizing anyone but himself. People are imprisoned even for minor violations, the minimum term of imprisonment is from three to seven years. People were thrown into prison for any small crime. In this way, the dungeons were filled with prisoners, and in order to free the dungeon, they took the prisoners out of the dungeon and executed them in groups. Especially during the time of the emir's father, the emir used to kill people loyal to Nasrullah and appropriate their property. He separated the common people and the slaves from the beginning. Ahmed Donish, who saw these events with his own eyes, expressed his opinion saying "Amir Muzaffar is stupid and short-sighted...", "During the reign of this mindless and bloodthirsty emir..."

Mirza Abdulazim Sami, unlike Ahmad Donish, was afraid to express his thoughts openly, "During the early period of Amir Muzaffar's rule, he wore the robe of justice and generosity. He treated other citizens of the country with amirs and soldiers with various gifts and treated them gently. "He had praiseworthy and good-natured qualities," he said.

Ahmad Donish openly explained the guilt of the emir, Tsarist Russia, and the khanate in the decline of the country. Ahmad Donish expressed his opinion about the occupation of the Khanate by the side of Tsarist Russia, and said that when Tashkent was under siege by the

Russians, Amir Muzaffar marched to Kogan, "It is shameful and shameful to oppose the Russians. "If I go against them, I will go straight to Moscow on my horse," he says with surprise.

As a result, as a result of the emir's reckless march to Kokhan, Tashkent was easily lost.

He spends one hundred thousand coins and twenty months from the treasury to build a protective wall as a border from Bukhara to Jizzakh so that the Russians do not threaten the territories of the Bukhara Emirate. Jizzakh stationed a number of troops around him and appointed Yaqub Qushbegi, who had never heard a gunshot in his life, had absolutely no knowledge of the military, and had never seen a battlefield, as the defense commander. As a result, he notes that soon Samarkand easily fell into the hands of the Russians.

Due to the wrong decision of the emir, an order was given to build fortress walls around Jizzakh, and military garrisons were established, as if to stop the Russian troops. The appointment of Yaqub Kushbegi, who had never heard a gunshot in his life, as the commander-in-chief worsened the situation. The soldiers were also ashamed to fight with such a leader. But while the thinker dwells on the conquest of the Bukhara Emirate in this way, he does not mention the military clashes between the Bukhara and Russian troops, especially the clashes in Kattakurgan, Panjshambe and Zirabulok.

In his treatise, Ahmad Donish discusses the disturbances in the emirate during the reign of Amir Daniyal, the management system of Amir Shahmurad, some events during the reign of Amir Haidar, the reign of Amir Husayn, Amir Umar, one of Amir Haidar's sons, Amir Nasrullah's seizure of power, Amir Muzaffar's management methods and highlights some events during the reign of Amir Abdulahad Khan.

Ahmad Donish's two works are mainly devoted to the problems of history and state administration. This is, first of all, *Nawadir-ul-Waqe*, which is the main and most important part of the "Political treatise", and "it takes the first place both in terms of the time of its creation and in terms of its importance. "*Nawadir-ul-Waqe*" occupies the main place among the chapters, and the topic in it is one of the main reasons that prompted the thinker to write the entire book.

Secondly, the Treatise is a historical source for the period in which the thinker lived.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedova Z. A. REFORMATIVE VIEWS OF AHMAD DONISH IN MODERNIZATION EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS IN THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA (XIX AND EARLY XX CENTURIES) //Journal of Social Research in Uzbekistan. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 01. – С. 42-51.
2. Akhmedova Z. A. PHILOSOPHY OF THE FIRST JADID AHMAD MAHDUM DONISH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758). – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 12. – С. 41-44.
3. Ахмедова З. А. Human existence in the works of medieval thinkers //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 1. – С. 857-859.
4. Ахмедова З. А. Астрономические взгляды Ахмада Дониш //Вестник науки и образования. – 2018. – №. 11 (47). – С. 44-46.
5. Akhmedova Z. A. ANALYSIS BY AHMAD DONISH ABOUT THE STATE ADMINISTRATION OF THE MANGYT RULERS //CURRENT RESEARCH

- JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758). – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 122-129.
6. Ахмедова З. А. XIX АСРНИНГ ИККИНЧИ ЯРМИДА ТУРКИСТОН ЎЛКАСИ МАДАНИЯТИ //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 7.
 7. Сагикызы А., Шуршитбай М., Ахмедова З. UPBRINGING AND EDUCATION AS FACTORS OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT //Адам элeмi. – 2021. – Т. 88. – №. 2. – С. 18-25.
 8. Akhmedova Z. A. AHMAD DONISH'S IDEAS ON IMPROVING PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION //Oriental Journal of Philology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 9-17.
 9. Azizovna A. Z. CULTURE OF TURKESTAN IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE 19 CENTURY //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
 10. Akhmedova Z. A. THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN EXISTENCE AND THE PROBLEM OF NATURE IN THE PHILOSOPHY OF AHMAD DONISH //Oriental Journal of Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 03. – С. 53-58.
 11. Alievna C. M. HISTORICAL SCIENCES //CUTTING EDGE-SCIENCE. – 2020. – С. 39.
 12. Akhmedova Z. A. ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF PHILOSOPHY IN THE LIFE OF SOCIETY //Наука, техника и образование. – 2020. – №. 11. – С. 39-41.